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ABSTRACT

Granular avalanches are dangerous phenomena characterized by the rapid gravity-driven motion of granular solids. The complex dynamics of these flows can be effectively modeled by a multilayer approach, which, however, requires particular attention to the derivation of the model equations in order to allow stable solutions. In this work, we use a well-posed multilayer model, in which the $\mu(I)$ -rheology is employed and a dilatancy law, depending on the inertial number I , is also taken into account, and systematically compare it with various laboratory experiments. The model, whose well-posedness is guaranteed by a physically based viscous regularization, describes the evolution of a preset number of superimposed granular layers. As the sidewall friction is relevant under most experimental conditions, the model is fitted here with suitable resistance terms. Moreover, non-trivial closures for the mass exchanges are introduced to avoid any unrealistic partitioning of the flow domain during the avalanche evolution, and, hence, guarantee a regular spatial discretization along the normal to flow direction. The velocity fields are compared with different experiments in unsteady state, and comparisons of both velocity and volume fraction profiles are provided with steady uniform flow experiments. The results confirm the good capabilities of the multilayer model and the underlying $\mu(I)$ -rheology in capturing the granular flow dynamics. The experimental volume fraction profiles are qualitatively well reproduced by the proposed dilatancy law, while an overestimation is observed only in the upper, more dilute flow region with a thickness of a few grain diameters.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Geophysical granular flows, like avalanches and debris flows, represent a major hazard for human activities and infrastructures (e.g., Iverson, 1997; Ancey, 2001; and Hungri *et al.*, 2001). A comprehensive physical understanding of such phenomena and their mathematical description are essential for the related risk assessment. In recent decades, many studies have focused on the dynamics of dry granular media and liquid-granular mixtures (Gray *et al.*, 1999; Aranson and Tsimring, 2002; Silbert *et al.*, 2003; da Cruz *et al.*, 2005; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Forterre, 2006; Gray and Ancey, 2009; Börzsönyi *et al.*, 2009; Gray and Edwards, 2014; Meng and Wang, 2016; Heß *et al.*, 2017; Kamrin, 2019; Tai *et al.*, 2019; Sarno *et al.*, 2021a; and Liu *et al.*, 2021). In addition to theoretical and field-scale research, laboratory

investigations are extremely useful to study the aspects of the granular dynamics that are difficult to isolate at large scales or are not fully captured by current mathematical models (e.g., GDR MiDi, 2004; Jop *et al.*, 2005; 2007; Pudasaini *et al.*, 2007; Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; 2018b; Meninno *et al.*, 2018; Jianbo *et al.*, 2020; and Sarno *et al.*, 2021c). In addition to the velocity field, another important quantity is the solid volume fraction that is strongly coupled with the dynamics of free-surface granular flows (e.g., Bagnold, 1954; Savage, 1979; and Josserand *et al.*, 2004). Very few laboratory studies have been devoted to developing noninvasive techniques for the estimation of the volume fraction (Capart *et al.*, 2002; Sheng *et al.*, 2011; Sarno *et al.*, 2016; Meninno *et al.*, 2018; and Sarno *et al.*, 2019a; 2020). While the volume fraction measurements are usually less accurate than the velocity

measurements (e.g., Pudasaini *et al.*, 2007; Thielicke and Stamhuis, 2014; Sarno *et al.*, 2018b; 2019b; and Thielicke and Sonntag, 2021), when available they represent valuable complementary data for better understanding the granular flow dynamics and also for the validation of mathematical models accounting for the effects of variable volume fraction (Carleo *et al.*, 2019; Sarno *et al.*, 2021c).

Though many efforts have been made toward developing a suitable constitutive law for describing the variety of granular flow regimes (e.g., Savage, 1984; Wang and Hutter, 2001; and Guo *et al.*, 2021), a unified rheology is still lacking because there are several properties of granular media (e.g., jamming transition, non-local effects, hysteresis, segregation, etc.) that cannot be reproduced in a manageable mathematical form. For the dense-collisional regime, most common in nature, the $\mu(I)$ -rheology (Pouliquen and Forterre, 2002; Jop *et al.*, 2005; 2006), which postulates a Coulomb friction-type law with the friction coefficient depending on the non-dimensional inertial number I (Savage, 1984; Ancey *et al.*, 1999), has accumulated robust experimental support (e.g., GDR MIDI, 2004; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Forterre, 2006; Gray and Edwards, 2014; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019). However, while the $\mu(I)$ -rheology has been successfully implemented into a Navier–Stokes-type model by Lagre *et al.* (2011), the incompressible three-dimensional (3D) model with the $\mu(I)$ -rheology is only well-posed for an intermediate range of I (Barker *et al.*, 2015).

A computationally more efficient depth-averaged approach (e.g., Grigorian *et al.*, 1967; Gray *et al.*, 1999; Hutter *et al.*, 2005; Tai and Kuo, 2008; Medina *et al.*, 2008; and Papa *et al.*, 2018) is often preferred over 3D models, especially for large field scale simulations. Yet, the computational advantages of the depth-averaged models come at the cost of a loss of detail along the transverse flow direction. Single-layer models are suitable for describing geophysical flows, if the velocity varies only weakly along the flow depth (e.g., Gray *et al.*, 1999; Hutter *et al.*, 2005). Conversely, they become inadequate if the velocity profiles are highly sheared or change in shape rapidly due to a rheological stratification (e.g., Armanini *et al.*, 2005). A stratification of this kind typically occurs when the magnitudes of frictional and collisional momentum exchange mechanisms vary strongly along the flow depth and is usually favored by the presence of an erodible bed or a narrow cross section (Jop *et al.*, 2005; Lanzoni *et al.*, 2017; and Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; 2021c). Within the framework of depth-averaged models, an improvement over single-layer models, aiming at better describing stratified flows and simultaneously keeping low computational costs compared to fully 3D models, is represented by two- and multi-layer models (Audusse, 2005; Chen *et al.*, 2007; Castro *et al.*, 2007; Luca *et al.*, 2009; Doyle *et al.*, 2010; La Rocca *et al.*, 2012; Sarno *et al.*, 2014; Fernandez-Nieto *et al.*, 2014; 2016; Meng *et al.*, 2017; Fernandez-Nieto *et al.*, 2018; and Sarno *et al.*, 2021a). Yet, a mathematical issue of multilayer models, also shared with multi-phase models (Keyfitz *et al.*, 2003), is their hyperbolicity loss under certain flow conditions, which is associated with short-wave Hadamard instabilities (e.g., Joseph and Saut, 1990; Greco *et al.*, 2008; and Abgrall and Karni, 2009). This important limitation, which also poses relevant open questions on the numerical convergence of the related numerical schemes, has been tried to be circumvented by various numerical or more physically based approaches (e.g., Holmas *et al.*, 2008; Abgrall and Karni, 2009; Castro *et al.*, 2011; Audusse *et al.*, 2011a; 2011b; Fernandez-Nieto *et al.*, 2014; Chiapolino and Saurel, 2018; Sarno *et al.*, 2017; Krvavica *et al.*, 2018; Etrati and Frigaard, 2018; and Sarno *et al.*, 2021a; 2021b).

Sarno *et al.* (2021a) introduced a compressible multilayer model based on the $\mu(I)$ -rheology and a viscous regularization derived from the same $\mu(I)$ -rheology. Also, in order to take into account the effects of variable volume fraction, the model implements a dilatancy law, depending on the inertial number I . A key mathematical advantage of the proposed model, over preexisting models with the $\mu(I)$ -rheology (e.g., Lagre *et al.*, 2011; Barker *et al.*, 2015; Fernandez-Nieto *et al.*, 2016; Martin *et al.*, 2017; and Zhankui *et al.*, 2022), is represented by its well-posedness for any value of the inertial number, I .

In this paper, the multilayer model by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) is employed and slightly adapted in order to allow reliable comparisons with typical laboratory experiments. Specifically, the effects of the side-walls (e.g., Jop *et al.*, 2005; Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019) are accounted for by introducing suitable friction terms. In contrast to Sarno *et al.* (2021a), non-trivial closures for the mass exchanges between the layers are considered here to prevent any unphysical partitioning of the flow domain during the avalanche evolution: namely, some layers may become much thinner than the other ones. In this way, a regular spatial discretization along the normal to flow direction is guaranteed.

Various experimental datasets, encompassing different geometries and flow conditions, are used for comparisons with the model predictions. A first comparison is carried out using the unsteady surface flows experiments by Jop *et al.* (2007). Another comparison is performed against dam-break experiments in a narrow steep chute, conducted at the National Cheng Kung University (Taiwan). Steady uniform experiments over an erodible bed, performed at the University of Salerno (Italy), are employed to compare both velocity and volume fraction profiles. In the latter experimental dataset, the velocity profiles were obtained by granular particle image velocimetry (g-PIV) (Sarno *et al.*, 2018b) similar to the other two datasets, while the volume fraction profiles were estimated by employing the stochastic-optical method (SOM) by Sarno *et al.* (2016; 2019a; 2020).

The scheme of this paper is as follows: In Sec. II, the multilayer model is briefly recalled, and the closures for the mass exchanges and the terms accounting for the sidewall friction are detailed. The numerical scheme is illustrated in Sec. III. The comparisons with the experiments are reported and discussed in Sec. IV. The conclusions are given in Sec. V.

II. MODEL EQUATIONS

In the first part (Secs. II A, II B 1, and II B 2), we recall the *continuum* mechanics approach and the multilayer model by Sarno *et al.* (2021a). For more details on the model derivation and its mathematical properties, we refer the reader to Sarno *et al.* (2021a). Subsequently, we introduce non-trivial closures for the mass exchanges (Sec. II B 3) and consider the sidewall effects (Sec. II B 4).

A. Governing equations and constitutive laws

A granular medium is composed of a large number of solid objects interacting with each other. Nonetheless, it can be conveniently regarded as a *continuum* of bulk density $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \rho_g \nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$, with ρ_g being the grain density and $\nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$ the solid volume fraction. In most geophysical flows, grains are sensibly incompressible, as the confining pressures are typically small (e.g., Savage, 1984). Hence, $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ varies only with $\nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$, which, in turn, depends on the granular dynamics.

The mass and momentum balances, involving the velocity $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the stress tensor $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and the volume fraction $\nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$, read as

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t \nu + \nabla \cdot (\nu \mathbf{u}) = 0, \\ \partial_t (\nu \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\nu \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \frac{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}}{\rho_g} = \nu \mathbf{g}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the tension-positive convention is adopted, $\nabla \cdot$ is the divergence operator, \otimes is the dyadic product, and \mathbf{g} is the gravity vector. The stress tensor in (1) can be decomposed as $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -p(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{T}^*(\mathbf{x}, t)$, with p being the isotropic pressure and $\mathbf{1}$ the identity matrix. Considering a Cartesian coordinate system Oxz with the x axis parallel to the downward slope rotated by an angle ζ to the horizontal and the z axis pointing upwards, the balance law (1) in a two-dimensional (2D) case yields the following scalar equations:

$$\partial_t \nu + \partial_x (\nu u_x) + \partial_z (\nu u_z) = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t (\nu u_x) + \partial_x (\nu u_x^2) + \partial_z (\nu u_x u_z) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_x p - \partial_x t_{xx}^* - \partial_z t_{xz}^*) \\ = \nu g \sin \zeta, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t (\nu u_z) + \partial_x (\nu u_x u_z) + \partial_z (\nu u_z^2) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_z p - \partial_x t_{zx}^* - \partial_z t_{zz}^*) \\ = -\nu g \cos \zeta, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where t_{ij}^* is the ij component of \mathbf{T}^* .

Equations (2)–(4) have to be equipped with a constitutive law. A well-established one for dense granular flows is the $\mu(I)$ -rheology (Jop et al., 2005; 2006) that postulates the viscoplastic relationship

$$\mathbf{T}^* = 2\eta(I, p)\mathbf{D} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\mu(I)p}{\|\mathbf{D}\|} \mathbf{D}. \quad (5)$$

In the above equation, $\mathbf{D} = 1/2(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T)$ is the strain-rate tensor, $\|\mathbf{D}\| = \sqrt{\mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D}}$ is the Frobenius tensor norm of \mathbf{D} , and η is a viscosity function, which increases linearly with p and also with a Coulomb-like friction coefficient μ , depending on the inertial number (Savage, 1984; Ancey et al., 1999)

$$I = \frac{\sqrt{2}d_g \|\mathbf{D}\|}{\sqrt{p/\rho_g}}, \quad (6)$$

with d_g being the characteristic grain diameter. Jop et al. (2005) experimentally found that

$$\mu(I) = \mu_s + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0/I + 1}, \quad (7)$$

where μ_s is the friction coefficient at zero shear rate, μ_2 is an upper bound for μ , and I_0 is a constant, corresponding to the value of I for which $\mu(I) = (\mu_s + \mu_2)/2$.

A closure for the volume fraction, ν , in Eqs. (2)–(4) is also required. The volume fraction of a granular medium typically decreases during a shearing deformation. This phenomenon is called *dilatancy* (Reynolds, 1885). For the slow shearing regime ($I < 0.20$), da Cruz et al. (2005) used molecular dynamics simulations to find the simple linear relationship, $\nu = \nu_{\max} - aI$, where a is a constant coefficient. This behavior has also been partially supported by additional numerical investigations (Börzsönyi et al., 2009) and experiments

(e.g., GDR MiDi, 2004; Carleo et al., 2019). Slightly modifying the formula by da Cruz et al. (2005), Sarno et al. (2021a) introduced the following equation of state (EOS):

$$\nu(I) = \nu_{\min} + \frac{\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min}}{1 + a'I}, \quad (8)$$

where ν_{\min} and ν_{\max} are, respectively, the lower and upper bounds for ν and a' is a new empirical parameter. For consistency with the formula by da Cruz et al. (2005) at small values of I , $a' = a/(\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min})$.

B. Multilayer approach

1. Model configuration

Adopting a multilayer approach (Audusse, 2005; Audusse et al., 2011b; Fernández-Nieto et al., 2016; and Sarno et al., 2021a), the granular avalanche is regarded as composed of a preset number, N , of superimposed layers. The partitioning of the flow domain is reported in Fig. 1. The generic i th layer occupies the subdomain, Ω_i , and has thickness, h_i . The velocity and the volume fraction in the generic layer i are denoted with $\mathbf{u}_i(x, z, t)$ and $\nu_i(x, z, t)$, respectively.

Following the same notation by Audusse (2011b), the equation of the generic interface, $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, between layers i and $i + 1$ reads as

$$\Gamma_{i+1/2}(x, z, t) = z - z_{i+1/2}(x, t) = z - \sum_{j=1}^i h_j(x, t) - b(x) = 0, \quad (9)$$

where b is the bed topography and $h_i(x, t) = z_{i+1/2}(x, t) - z_{i-1/2}(x, t)$. While the free surface, $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$, is a material interface, the internal interfaces are assumed to be permeable to mass exchanges. Hence, the kinematic boundary conditions (KBCs) immediately below and above the generic interface, $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, marked by the superscripts “−” and “+,” respectively, read as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\Gamma_{i+1/2}}{dt} \Big|^- &= -\partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + u_{z,i} = \frac{M_{i+1/2}}{\rho_g \nu_i} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|, \\ \frac{d\Gamma_{i+1/2}}{dt} \Big|^+ &= -\partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i+1} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + u_{z,i+1} = \frac{M_{i+1/2}}{\rho_g \nu_{i+1}} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

FIG. 1. The partitioning of the flow domain according to the multilayer approach (Sarno et al., 2021a).

In the above equations, $M_{i+1/2}$ is the mass flux per unit length of the interface and $|\nabla\Gamma_{i+1/2}| = \sqrt{1 + (\partial_x z_{i+1/2})^2}$. $M_{i+1/2} > 0$ if a net mass flux goes from layer i into layer $i + 1$. The free surface, $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$, is traction free: $\mathbf{T}_{N+1/2}\mathbf{n}_{N+1/2} = \mathbf{0}$. The dynamic boundary conditions (DBC) at the layers' interfaces are derived from the $\mu(I)$ -rheology, (5), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{T}_i\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{T}_i\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2})\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{2}\mu(I)p_i}{\|\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^-\|} [\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^-\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^-\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2})\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}], \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{T}_{i+1}\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{i+1}\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2})\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{2}\mu(I)p_{i+1}}{\|\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+\|} [\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2})\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}], \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} = \nabla\Gamma_{i+1/2}/|\nabla\Gamma_{i+1/2}|$ is the unit normal vector to $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. Following the notation by Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2014), the terms $\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^\pm$ stand for suitable approximations of the strain-rate tensor from below and above $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. For $M_{i+1/2} = 0$, the right-hand sides (RHS) of (11) and (12) are equal; conversely, for $M_{i+1/2} \neq 0$ a stress jump occurs across $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$ (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2014),

$$\llbracket \mathbf{T} \rrbracket \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} = \llbracket \mathbf{u} \rrbracket M_{i+1/2}, \quad (13)$$

with $\llbracket f \rrbracket = f^+ - f^-$. Sarno *et al.* (2021a) provided suitable expressions for the RHS of (11) and (12), consistent with the Rankine–Hugoniot condition, (13). Equation (12) also holds at the bed surface, $\Gamma_{1/2}$, if the bed is made of the same granular material. If conversely there is a solid bedrock, a different basal DBC, depending on both the granular material and the basal surface, needs to be defined.

2. Resultant partial differential equation (PDE) system

The multilayer model equations were derived in Sarno *et al.* (2021a) by depth-averaging Eqs. (2)–(4) along each layer and by taking into account the various boundary conditions (10)–(12). Subsequently, as the granular avalanches are typically thin and elongated, the depth-averaged equations were further simplified by first-order asymptotic analysis for the parameter $\varepsilon = H/L \ll 1$, with H and L , respectively, being the typical depth and length scales of the avalanche (e.g., Tai *et al.*, 2012; Sarno *et al.*, 2014). Namely, the terms smaller than $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ were neglected in the resulting partial differential equation (PDE) system. Moreover, it was postulated that the velocity and volume fraction fields within each layer are constant to leading order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$, and, hence, the momentum correction coefficient (Boussinesq coefficient) was set equal to 1 for each layer (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a). These assumptions also greatly simplify the calculations of the momentum fluxes between neighbor layers [cf. Eq. (16)] without loss

of generality, since the spatial resolution along the normal to flow direction can be arbitrarily increased by increasing the number of layers N . From the asymptotic expansion of the z -component momentum equations, a hydrostatic pressure distribution with piecewise constant pressure gradients, depending on the volume fraction, was obtained [see Eq. (39) in Sarno *et al.* (2021a)]. To guarantee the model well-posedness, an approximation of the higher-than- $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ term accounting for the in-plane stress gradient was retained in the x -component momentum equations. Without loss of generality, Sarno *et al.* (2021a) studied the key mathematical properties of the multilayer model by assuming immiscible layers. However, for practical applications, this assumption may lead to an unphysical partitioning of the avalanche, as it allows that some layers locally become much thinner than the others. Here, we allow non-zero mass exchanges, where the related closures will be given in Sec. II B 3. With reference to the generic i th layer, the resulting PDE system reads as

$$\tau_{relax}(\partial_t \bar{v}_i + u_i^* \partial_x \bar{v}_i) = \bar{v}_i - \bar{v}_{i,EOS} + \ell^2 \partial_{xx} \bar{v}_i, \quad (14)$$

$$\partial_t(h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i}) + \partial_x(h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i}) = \frac{1}{\rho_g} (M_{x,i-1/2} - M_{x,i+1/2}), \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_t(h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i}) + \partial_x \left(\frac{(h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i})^2}{h_i \bar{v}_i} \right) + \partial_x \left(\frac{g \cos \zeta (h_i \bar{v}_i)^2}{2 \bar{v}_i} \right) \\ &+ g \cos \zeta \left[\frac{h_i \bar{v}_i}{\bar{v}_i} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j \right) + h_i \bar{v}_i \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{h_j \bar{v}_j}{\bar{v}_j} \right) \right] \\ &= gh_i \bar{v}_i (\sin \zeta - \cos \zeta \partial_x b) + \frac{d_g (\mu_s + \mu_2) \sqrt{g \cos \zeta}}{I_0 \nu_0} \\ &\times \partial_x \left(\bar{v}_i h_i \sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j} + \frac{\bar{v}_i h_i}{2} \partial_x \left(\frac{h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i}}{h_i \bar{v}_i} \right) \right) \\ &- \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\tilde{t}_{xz}^*|_{i-1/2} - \tilde{t}_{xz}^*|_{i+1/2}) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (u_{i-1/2,downwind} M_{x,i-1/2} \\ &- u_{i+1/2,downwind} M_{x,i+1/2}), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where the unknowns are the layer-averaged volume fractions, $\bar{v}_i = (1/h_i) \int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} \nu_i(x, z, t) dz$, the layer masses, $h_i \bar{v}_i$, and the layer-averaged momenta, $h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} = \int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} \nu_i(x, z, t) u_{x,i}(x, z, t) dz$.

Equation (14) describes the transport of \bar{v}_i by the advection velocity, u_i^* , (of order of $\bar{u}_{x,i}$) and its concurrent relaxation toward the equilibrium, $\bar{v}_{i,EOS}$, according to the relaxation time, τ_{relax} . In practice, the relaxation process toward the equilibrium is assumed to be dominant over the advection process (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a), so that a stiff relaxation is used in the numerical computations (i.e., τ_{relax} is assumed to be smaller than the time step, Δt). The equilibrium, $\bar{v}_{i,EOS}$, is calculated by the following discretized version (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a) of the dilatancy law, (8):

$$\bar{v}_{i,EOS} = \frac{-1 + a' \nu_{\min}(\bar{I}_i / \bar{v}_{i,EOS}) + \sqrt{1 + (a')^2 \nu_{\min}^2(\bar{I}_i / \bar{v}_{i,EOS})^2 - 2a' \nu_{\min}(\bar{I}_i / \bar{v}_{i,EOS}) + 4a' \nu_{\max}(\bar{I}_i / \bar{v}_{i,EOS})}}{2a'(\bar{I}_i / \bar{v}_{i,EOS})}. \quad (17)$$

In the above equation, \bar{I}_i is an approximation of the layer-averaged I in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{I}_i(x, t) &\approx \frac{d_g [|\bar{u}_{x,i+1} - \bar{u}_{x,i-1}| / (h_i + h_{i-1}/2 + h_{i+1}/2) + \delta]}{\sqrt{\bar{p}_i / \rho_g}} \\ &\approx \frac{d_g [h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} \bar{u}_{x,i+1} / h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} - h_{i-1} \bar{v}_{i-1} \bar{u}_{x,i-1} / h_{i-1} \bar{v}_{i-1}] / (h_i \bar{v}_i + h_{i-1} \bar{v}_{i-1} / 2 + h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} / 2) + \delta]}{\sqrt{\bar{p}_i / \rho_g}} \bar{v}_i, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where δ is a small positive constant. For the lowermost and uppermost layers, \bar{I} are approximated by extrapolation as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{I}_1(x, t) &\approx I_{1/2}(x, t) \approx d_g [|\bar{u}_{x,2} - \bar{u}_{x,1}| / (h_2 \bar{v}_2 / 2 \\ &\quad + h_1 \bar{v}_1 / 2) + \delta] / \sqrt{\bar{p}_{1/2} / \rho_g} \bar{v}_1, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{I}_N(x, t) &\approx I_{N-1/2}(x, t) \approx d_g [|\bar{u}_{x,N} - \bar{u}_{x,N-1}| / (h_N \bar{v}_N / 2 \\ &\quad + h_{N-1} \bar{v}_{N-1} / 2) + \delta] / \sqrt{\bar{p}_{N-1/2} / \rho_g} \bar{v}_N. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Equation (14) also incorporates a diffusion-like term $\ell^2 \partial_{xx} \bar{v}_i$, aimed at describing possible non-local effects caused by the formation of force chains inside the granular medium (e.g., Bouzid *et al.*, 2013; 2015; Kamrin, 2019). In this respect, similar to the I -gradient model proposed by Bouzid *et al.* (2013), Eq. (14) can be regarded as a Ginzburg–Landau-type equation of phase transition with order parameter, \bar{v}_i , where ℓ is a characteristic interaction length depending on the flow regime and the grain properties. In this work, we simply assume $\ell = 0$.

Equations (15) and (16) are, respectively, the layer-averaged mass and momentum equations, where $M_{x,i\pm 1/2} = M_{i\pm 1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i\pm 1/2}|$ are the mass fluxes per unit length of interface $\Gamma_{i\pm 1/2}$ projected along x (Sarno *et al.*, 2014; 2021a), and $u_{i\pm 1/2, \text{downwind}}$ are velocities, evaluated above/below $\Gamma_{i\pm 1/2}$ in a downwind fashion. Namely, if $M_{x,i+1/2} \geq 0$, $u_{i+1/2, \text{downwind}} = \bar{u}_{x,i}$, and if $M_{x,i+1/2} < 0$, $u_{i+1/2, \text{downwind}} = \bar{u}_{x,i+1}$. In Eq. (16), $\tilde{\tau}_{xz}|_{i\pm 1/2}$ represent the single-valued shear stresses at $\Gamma_{i\pm 1/2}$, which, according to the constitutive law, (5), and after some algebraic manipulations, can be written as (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\tilde{\tau}_{xz}|_{i\pm 1/2}}{\rho_g} &= \mu_s \left(g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j \right) \right) \frac{\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}}{|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta} \\ &\quad + \frac{d_g (\mu_2 - \mu_s)}{\left(I_0 + d_g (|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta) \right) / \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j \right)}} \\ &\quad \times \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j \right)} \Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

In the above equation, the quantity $\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}$ is a central second-order approximation of $\partial_z u_x|_{i+1/2}$ at the interface, $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_z u_x|_{i+1/2} &\approx \Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2} = \frac{\bar{u}_{x,i+1} - \bar{u}_{x,i}}{(h_i + h_{i+1})/2} \\ &= \frac{h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} \bar{u}_{x,i+1} / h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} - h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i}{(h_i \bar{v}_i / \bar{v}_i + h_{i+1} \bar{v}_{i+1} / \bar{v}_{i+1})/2}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

and, for the lowermost interface, $\Gamma_{1/2}$,

$$\partial_z u_x|_{1/2} \approx \Delta_z u_x|_{1/2} = \frac{\bar{u}_{x,1}}{h_{1/2}} = \frac{h_1 \bar{v}_1 \bar{u}_{x,1} / h_1 \bar{v}_1}{h_1 \bar{v}_1 / \bar{v}_1 / 2}. \quad (23)$$

To avoid singularities at zero shear rate, in (21) $|\partial_z \hat{u}_x|$ is increased by the small constant $\delta = 10^{-6} \text{s}^{-1}$ (e.g., Bercovier and Engelman, 1980; Martino and Papa, 2008; Fernández-Nieto *et al.*, 2016; and Lin and Yang, 2021).

It is worth remarking that Eqs. (15) and (16) contain not only conservative terms, resembling the structure of the classical shallow water model (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a), but also the non-conservative terms

$$g \cos \zeta \left[\frac{h_i \bar{v}_i}{\bar{v}_i} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j \right) + h_i \bar{v}_i \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{h_j \bar{v}_j}{\bar{v}_j} \right) \right]. \quad (24)$$

The terms, (24), account for the pressure effects exerted on the generic i th layer by the other layers. As shown by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) and also in common with the two-layer models (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2017; 2021b), such effects are responsible for the possible hyperbolicity loss of the advective part of the PDE system under certain flow conditions. To efficiently damp out the short-wave instabilities, possibly arising from this hyperbolicity loss, an original feature of the proposed multilayer model is represented by the diffusion-like term, incorporated in (16) and accounting for the effects of the in-plane stress gradients

$$\psi \partial_x \left(\bar{v}_i h_i \sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j} + \frac{\bar{v}_i h_i}{2} \partial_x \left(\frac{h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i}}{h_i \bar{v}_i} \right) \right). \quad (25)$$

In the above equation, the diffusion-like coefficient, $\psi = d_g (\mu_s + \mu_2) \sqrt{g \cos \zeta} / I_0 \nu_0$, is constant, with ν_0 being the volume fraction at I_0 . Sarno *et al.* (2021a) showed that, while the term, (25), is of order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{1+\beta})$ with $0 < \beta < 1$, and, hence, can be neglected in a first-order model, it is crucial to ensure the model well-posedness for any value of I . Specifically, Sarno *et al.* (2021a) performed a short-wave stability analysis, proving that the model well-posedness holds for any closure of the source terms, even non-zero mass exchanges, provided that such closures are made to depend only on the unknown function, $\mathbf{q} = (\{\bar{v}_i, \bar{v}_i h_i, \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} h_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N})^T$, but not on its spatial and temporal derivatives. Indeed, it can be easily verified that in the linearized PDE system associated with a small perturbation, $\delta \mathbf{q}$, around a generic base state, \mathbf{q}_B , the quantities, resulting from the source terms depending on \mathbf{q} , are of order $\mathcal{O}(k^{-1})$ with k being the wave number of the perturbation, and, hence, they can be neglected in the short-wave stability analysis, carried out in the limit of $k \rightarrow \infty$ (see Sec. IV B in Sarno *et al.*, 2021a). Therefore, the well-posedness properties of the multilayer

model, studied in detail by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) with reference to the special case of immiscible layers, still hold for the current version of the model, equipped with the closures and modifications hereafter reported in Secs. II B 3 and II B 4. This is a key advantage over preexisting multilayer and 3D models with the $\mu(I)$ -rheology that are only conditionally well-posed (Barker *et al.*, 2015).

3. Closures for the mass exchanges

Considering the Reynolds time-averaged velocity field in a regular channel geometry without obstacles, a granular flow is typically characterized by a physical stratification (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; Carleo *et al.*, 2019; and Sarno *et al.*, 2021c). Indeed, the partitioning of the flow domain, postulated by the multilayer approach, is physically supported by the prevalence of the stream-wise velocities over the much smaller transverse velocities. Yet, considering unsteady flows or shorter time intervals, the flow stratification in the model can only be regarded as a simplification of reality, since mass exchanges between the layers may occur owing to velocity fluctuations and sudden changes in the velocity field. In this general case, the assumption of perfectly immiscible layers (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a) appears unrealistic.

Here, we introduce a simple relaxation approach for the layer masses, aimed at achieving a mass redistribution among the layers during the numerical simulation. This approach prevents some layers from becoming locally much thinner than the others and, hence, guarantees an almost uniform spatial discretization along the transverse flow direction. The following closures are proposed:

$$\begin{cases} M_{x,1/2} = 0, \\ M_{x,i\pm 1/2} = -\frac{\rho_g}{\tau_{relax,reb}} \left[i \sum_{k=1}^N (h_k \bar{v}_k) / N - \sum_{j=1}^i (h_j \bar{v}_j) \right], \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where $\tau_{relax,reb}$ is a relaxation time for the mass rebalance among all N layers, i.e., the characteristic time required to restore the generic layer mass, $h_i \bar{v}_i$, to the averaged value, $\sum_{k=1}^N (h_k \bar{v}_k) / N$. Namely, the mass exchanges, $M_{x,i\pm 1/2}$, are designed to redistribute occasional mass excesses toward the other layers. From (26), it can be verified that $M_{x,N+1/2} = 0$, consistent with the material free surface. In the absence of a specific calibration, we assume that $\tau_{relax,reb}$ is constant, independent from the flow dynamics. After several preliminary tests, carried out in the range $\tau_{relax,reb} \in [10^{-2}\text{s}, 10^0\text{s}]$, we found that the numerical solution is only weakly influenced by $\tau_{relax,reb}$ with small differences observed only during the transient. In the following simulations, we will use $\tau_{relax,reb} = 10^{-1}\text{s}$.

4. Sidewall resistances

In laboratory experiments, where the granular material flows through a cross section of finite width, the sidewalls usually play a significant role (e.g., Jop *et al.*, 2005; Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019). Their effects are twofold. Since in real-world situations the sidewalls are never frictionless, they are able to absorb a certain amount of momentum. In a rectangular channel, the relative magnitudes of the sidewall resistances, compared to the basal resistances, are found to increase approximately with h/W , where h is the flow depth and W is the channel width (e.g., Roberts, 1969; Savage and Hutter, 1991; Jop *et al.*, 2005; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, the sidewalls

represent geometrical boundaries for the flow and, thus, also influence the flow dynamics indirectly. To this regard, a non-intuitive phenomenon is that the wider is the channel, the more the velocity field deviates from a purely 2D shear flow (Jop *et al.*, 2005; Maneval *et al.*, 2005; and Baker *et al.*, 2016). Under certain flow conditions, even a secondary circulation may develop in a sufficiently wide cross section (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; Carleo *et al.*, 2019). These complex 3D effects cannot be captured by a 2D model. Nonetheless, for an appropriate comparison between the multilayer model and the experiments, it is crucial to consider the sidewall resistances, which may significantly influence the velocity profiles by causing the progressive shift from a Bagnold convex shape (Bagnold, 1954; Silbert *et al.*, 2003) toward a linear shape, and eventually to a concave shape with a lower exponential tail (Komatsu *et al.*, 2001; Jop *et al.*, 2005; and Sarno *et al.*, 2018a). Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2018) showed that a clear advantage of the multilayer approach, over single-layer models, is represented by the capability of selectively taking into account the sidewall effects at different depths.

With reference to a flume with a rectangular cross section of width W , a well-established way to account for the sidewall resistances is to simply consider a zero-order rate-independent Coulomb-friction (e.g., Roberts, 1969; Savage and Hutter, 1991; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Sarno *et al.*, 2013; Fernández-Nieto *et al.*, 2018; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019). Implementing this approach into the multilayer model and considering the hydrostatic pressure distribution postulated by the model, the sidewall resistances for the generic i th layer are described by the following term, which is added to the RHS of Eq. (16):

$$\begin{aligned} r_{side,i} &= -2 \frac{\mu_{side}}{W} \bar{p}_i \text{sgn} \bar{u}_{x,i} \\ &= -2 \frac{\mu_{side}}{W} g \cos \zeta \left[\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j + \frac{\bar{v}_i h_i}{2} \right] \frac{h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i}{|h_i \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i|}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Here, \bar{p}_i is the depth-averaged pressure in the i th layer, and μ_{side} is an effective friction coefficient between the sidewall and the granular medium. While μ_{side} can be formally written as $\tan \varphi_{side}$, with φ_{side} being an angle of friction, it should be noted that it also incorporates an empirical correction factor (typically < 1) that has to be calibrated on the specific experimental data and, in general, takes into account all the uncertainties of the Coulomb-friction model, e.g., a non-unit earth pressure coefficient, electrostatic effects, friction decrease due to rolling friction mechanisms (Roberts, 1969; Carleo *et al.*, 2019). Again, it is worth mentioning that the introduction in Eq. (16) of the additional source terms, (27), depending on the unknown function, $\mathbf{q} = (\{\bar{v}_i, \bar{v}_i h_i, \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} h_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N})^T$, but not on its derivatives, does not change the well-posedness properties of the multilayer model, studied in detail by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) under simplified conditions (zero mass exchanges and no sidewall friction).

III. NUMERICAL SCHEME

The numerical scheme, similar to that illustrated by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) with the addition of the mass exchanges and the sidewall effects, is described here. For ease of notation, the model equations, (14)–(16), together with the closures for the mass exchanges, (26), and the sidewall resistances, (27), are rewritten in quasi-linear form as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{q} + (\partial_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{A}_{non-cons}) \partial_x \mathbf{q} \\ = \mathbf{s}_{EOS}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{topo}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{res}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{res,side}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{m}_{fluxes} \\ + \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}), \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = (\{\bar{v}_i, \bar{v}_i h_i, \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} h_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N})^T$ is the unknown vector, $\partial_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{f}$ is the $3N \times 3N$ Jacobian matrix of the shallow-water-type conservative fluxes, \mathbf{f} , and $\mathbf{A}_{non-cons}$ is the $3N \times 3N$ pseudo-Jacobian matrix (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a) containing the non-conservative terms, (24). The source term in the RHS of Eq. (28) is composed of various contributions. \mathbf{s}_{EOS} collects the source terms of Eq. (14); \mathbf{s}_{topo} contains the topographic terms, $g h_i \bar{v}_i (\sin \zeta - \cos \zeta \partial_x b)$, of Eq. (16); \mathbf{s}_{res} accounts for the resistances at the interfaces and at the bed; and \mathbf{s}_{diff} collects the diffusion-like terms, (25). Additionally, $\mathbf{s}_{res,side}$ collects the sidewall resistances, (27), and \mathbf{m}_{fluxes} stands for the source terms of Eq. (15) and the momentum exchanges due to the mass fluxes of Eq. (16), $1/\rho_g (u_{i-1/2,downwind} M_{x,i-1/2} - u_{i+1/2,downwind} M_{x,i+1/2})$, where the mass fluxes $M_{x,i \pm 1/2}$ are calculated through the closures, (26).

For the numerical integration of (28), we consider a uniform mesh size, Δx . The time step, Δt , has to fulfill the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition, where a global bound of the eigenvalue spectrum is given by the following formula (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a):

$$\max(|\lambda|) \leq \max_x \left(\max_i (|u_i|) + \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min_i (\bar{v}_i)} \right). \quad (29)$$

With reference to the generic time-point j and the spatial cell r , the numerical solution is denoted by \mathbf{Q}_r^j , while the intermediate solutions are $\mathbf{Q}_r^I, \mathbf{Q}_r^{II}$, etc. The following time-splitting approach (e.g., LeVeque, 2004) is employed:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stage I: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^j, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{m}_{fluxes} \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^I, \\ \text{Stage II: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^I, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{s}_{res} + \mathbf{s}_{res,side} \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{II}, \\ \text{Stage III: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^{II}, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}) \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{III}, \\ \text{Stage IV: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^{III}, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{topo} \Rightarrow_{\Delta t} \mathbf{Q}_r^{IV}, \\ \text{Stage V: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^{IV}, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}) \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^V, \\ \text{Stage VI: } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^V, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{s}_{res} + \mathbf{s}_{res,side} \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{VI}, \\ \text{Stage VII } \mathbf{q}(t = t^j) &= \mathbf{Q}_r^{VI}, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{m}_{fluxes} \Rightarrow_{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{(j+1)*}, \\ \text{Stage VIII: } (\bar{v}_i)_r^{j+1} &= (\bar{v}_{i,EOS})_r^{(j+1)*} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Q}_r^{j+1}. \end{aligned} \quad 30$$

In the first seven stages, the layer-averaged volume fractions, \bar{v}_i , are treated explicitly. At stages I and VII, the effects of the mass exchanges are calculated through an explicit scheme, where the numerical stability is guaranteed by the condition $\Delta t/2 \leq \tau_{relax,reb} = 10^{-1}$ s. In the rare case that $\Delta t/2 > \tau_{relax,reb}$, a time-marching procedure with a time sub-step smaller than $\tau_{relax,reb}$ is activated.

Then, an iterative scheme is employed at stages II and VI for solving the ordinary differential equation (ODE) with \mathbf{s}_{res} and $\mathbf{s}_{res,side}$. Specifically, a semi-implicit Euler scheme is used, where the quantities in the shear stress formula, (21), are calculated explicitly, except for the factor $\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}$ that is treated implicitly (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a). Likewise, in the term of the sidewall resistances, (27), the factor,

$h_i \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i$, is treated implicitly, while the denominator, $|h_i \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i|$, is evaluated explicitly and is increased by $\delta = 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to avoid singularity at zero shear rate. At each iteration of the semi-implicit scheme, the solution of the predictor stage, obtained by solving a $N \times N$ tri-diagonal linear system, is used in the subsequent corrector stage to estimate the explicit quantities. The iterative procedure stops when the L_2 -norm of the relative variations of the velocities becomes smaller than a convergence threshold, set to 10^{-4} m/s .

The diffusion-like term, \mathbf{s}_{diff} , accounted for at stages III and V, is treated in an explicit fashion where the second-order derivatives are approximated by $(\partial_{xx} f)_r^{n-1} = (f_{r+1}^{n-1} - 2f_r^{n-1} + f_{r-1}^{n-1})/\Delta x^2 + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2)$ and the non-linear terms by $(\partial_x f \partial_x g)_r^{n-1} = (f_{r+1}^{n-1} - f_{r-1}^{n-1})(g_{r+1}^{n-1} - g_{r-1}^{n-1})/\Delta x^2 + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2)$ with the superscript $n-1$ denoting the solution of the previous stage. For the numerical stability, a time-marching approach with $\Delta t_{multi-step,i} \leq \Delta t/2$ is typically necessary at these stages (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a). Specifically, for each layer, it is required that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t_{multi-step,i} \\ \leq \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\Delta x^2}{\psi \max_x \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j + \bar{v}_i h_i / 2 \max(1, |h_i \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} / h_i \bar{v}_i|)} \right)}}. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

At stage IV, the advection term, $\mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q}$, and topographic terms, \mathbf{s}_{topo} , are accounted for by a finite volume scheme using the lateralized Harten–Lax–van Leer (LHLL) approximate Riemann solver (Harten *et al.*, 1983; Fraccarollo *et al.*, 2003), which was also employed by Sarno *et al.* (2014, 2017) in the context of two-layer models. High-resolution in space is obtained by a MUSCL predictor-corrector treatment (van Leer, 1977) based on a minmod-limited linear reconstruction (Fraccarollo *et al.*, 2003). Analogous to Sarno *et al.* (2021a), the following formulas are employed in the LHLL scheme as lower and upper bounds for the eigenvalue set:

$$\begin{aligned} S_R &= \min \left(0, \min u_i - \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min \bar{v}_i} \right), \\ S_L &= \max \left(0, \max u_i + \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min \bar{v}_i} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Finally, $(\bar{v}_i)_r^{j+1}$ are updated at stage VIII by stiff relaxation: namely, they are calculated by the EOS formula, (17), as a function of the numerical solution of stage VII. Analogous to that reported in detail by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) with reference to a simplified version of the PDE system, the well-posedness of the multilayer model and the regular behavior of its numerical solution have also been confirmed by the systematic convergence of the numerical scheme with the mesh refinement.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISONS

In this section, the multilayer model is tested against several laboratory experiments. In Sec. IV A, the model predictions are compared with transient surface flows (Jop *et al.*, 2007). In Sec. IV B, the model is tested against dam-break flows in an inclined channel. Finally, in Sec. IV C, the velocity and volume fraction profiles, predicted by the model,

are compared with the experimental measurements of steady uniform chute flows over an erodible bed.

A. Transient surface flows

Here, the multilayer model, (28), is compared with the experimental data by Jop *et al.* (2007) and with the numerical simulations by the 3D $\mu(I)$ model (Jop *et al.*, 2006; 2007). This dataset, already used as a benchmark by Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2016), consists of quasi-2D unsteady surface flows in a narrow flume with width, $W = 1$ cm, and a rough bottom. The granular medium is made of glass spheres with $d_g = 0.53$ mm and an angle of repose, $\varphi_s = 20.9^\circ$. After tilting the flume at an angle higher than φ_s , the static granular pile, located inside the flume, was set in motion. Various bed inclinations $26.1^\circ \leq \zeta \leq 32.15^\circ$ were investigated to study the transition between the lower static and the upper flowing regions. The evolution of the velocity profile, corresponding to an intermediate region of the flume with almost spatially uniform conditions, was captured from the sidewall by a high-speed camera and by subsequent particle image velocimetry (PIV) analysis (e.g., Pudasaini *et al.*, 2007). These measurements were compared by Jop *et al.* (2007) with a 3D model implementing the $\mu(I)$ -rheology and Coulomb friction resistances at the sidewalls (Jop *et al.*, 2006). The rheological parameters, used in the 3D simulations, were previously obtained by calibration in similar laboratory conditions (Jop *et al.*, 2005): $\mu_s = \tan(20.9^\circ)$, $\mu_b = \tan(32.76^\circ)$, $I_0 = 0.279$, and the sidewall friction was set to $\mu_{side} = \tan(13.1^\circ)$.

Since the 3D simulations were performed with $\nu = 0.6$, for ease of comparison, the multilayer model was initially run with constant volume fraction, $\nu = 0.6$. Moreover, identical rheological parameters and sidewall friction as in Jop *et al.* (2007) were used. The spatial domain is $x \in [0, 1.1]$ m with a no-slip basal boundary condition and nonreflecting boundary conditions at $x = 0$ and $x = 1.1$ m. The initial conditions read as

$$h = \sum_{i=1}^N h_i(x, 0) = 40 d_g = 0.0212 \text{ m}, \quad \bar{u}_i(x, 0) = 0, \quad \bar{v}_i(x, 0) = 0.6. \quad (33)$$

The simulations were carried out with $N = 80$. For computational convenience, the initial deposit was set equal to $h = 40 d_g$ (with $h_i = 0.000265$ m). By trying different initial depths from $20 d_g$ to $160 d_g$, it was preliminarily verified that the thickness of the deposit does not influence the numerical results, provided that it is greater than the maximum thickness of the surface flow and, hence, the erosion process during the transient does not reach the proximity of the fixed bed. A spatial discretization with $\Delta x = 0.1$ m was chosen, while the time step was set equal to $\Delta t = 10^{-4}$ s to ensure the fulfillment of the CFL condition and a good accuracy of the ODE solver (cf. Sec. III).

With reference to the bed inclinations $\zeta = 26.1^\circ$ and $\zeta = 32.15^\circ$, the comparisons with increasing time between experimental and modeled velocity profiles are reported in Fig. 2. The investigated granular flows can be regarded as approximately 2D owing to the narrow cross section, $W = 19 d_g$ (Jop *et al.*, 2005). However, it is worth stressing that, while the experimental and numerical data by the 3D model (Jop *et al.*, 2007) are referred to the sidewall, the results by the multilayer model are an average in the transverse direction, taking into account the sidewall effects only in a width-averaged sense (cf. Sec. II B 4). As shown in Fig. 2, and also in agreement with Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2016), it is comforting that the multilayer model yields unsteady velocity profiles very similar to the ones obtained by the more computationally expensive 3D model. To this regard, it is worth recalling that the multilayer approach is based on several simplifying assumptions, including the long-wave approximation (e.g., Gray *et al.*, 1999; Hutter *et al.*, 2005; Tai and Kuo, 2008; and Jianbo *et al.*, 2020), and, hence, is expected to provide a relatively inferior description of the flow field compared to fully 3D models (Jop *et al.*, 2006; Lagrée *et al.*, 2011; Martin *et al.*, 2017; and Zhankui *et al.*, 2022). Nonetheless, the main advantages of the multilayer model are the lower computational costs (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a), especially useful for large scale numerical simulations, and the capability of naturally capturing the evolution of the free surface without recurring to special numerical treatments (such as the volume-of-fluid or the level-set methods), which are conversely necessary in 3D models using Eulerian meshes (e.g., Lagrée *et al.*, 2011; Zhankui *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, as the multilayer model is well-posed for any value of the inertial number, its numerical solution regularly

FIG. 2. Comparisons with increasing time between experimental and modeled velocity profiles. (a) $\zeta = 26.10^\circ$ (time points: $t = 0.0088$ s, $t = 0.1110$ s, and $t = 1.2211$ s); (b) $\zeta = 32.15^\circ$ ($t = 0.0169$ s, $t = 0.0551$ s, $t = 0.1779$ s, $t = 0.5720$ s, and $t = 1.2865$ s). The arrows indicate the direction of increasing t .

converges with the mesh refinement (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a), different from the conditionally well-posed models based on the Navier-Stokes equations with the unmodified $\mu(I)$ -rheology (Barker *et al.*, 2015). The numerical results are also in reasonably good agreement with the experiments, especially for $\zeta = 32.15^\circ$ [Fig. 2(b)]. Interestingly, it can be noted that, as t increases, both the 3D model and the multilayer model yield increasingly better agreement with the experimental data, which are more evident for the case of the slower experiment [Fig. 2(a)]. We believe that the relatively worse accord at the initial stages, which is common to both models, is mainly due to the limitations of the underlying $\mu(I)$ -rheology, which was initially introduced in the literature as a phenomenological theory for describing the asymptotic steady state of dense granular flows (Pouliquen and Forterre, 2002; Jop *et al.*, 2005). Namely, as signaled by Jop *et al.* (2007), the $\mu(I)$ rheological model is less accurate in quantitatively describing the transient stages from an initial state of rest and the slow regime. This is also partly due to the fact that the $\mu(I)$ -rheology with a rate-independent Coulomb friction at the sidewalls predicts a zero velocity from a finite depth (Jop *et al.*, 2005) and, hence, is unable to fully capture the exponential tail in the lower creep flow region (Komatsu *et al.*, 2001). Moreover, the model with the $\mu(I)$ -rheology neglects the non-local grain interactions (e.g., Bouzid *et al.*, 2015; Kamrin, 2019), expected to be more relevant in the slow regime, and is based on an isotropic pressure distribution, whereas non-unit earth-pressure coefficients would be more appropriate in the quasi-static stages of the granular motion. Additionally, the discrepancies in the transient of the slow flow [Fig. 2(a)] could also be partially explained by the fact that the deviations from a 2D flow typically increase with decreasing velocity, as observed by Sarno *et al.* (2018a) in a similar laboratory setup (see also Sec. IV C).

Subsequently, we performed further numerical simulations with variable ν . Jop *et al.* (2007) observed a weak dilatancy, corresponding to a lift of the free surface of a few grain diameters during the transient flow, but no volume fraction measurements were provided. Without a calibration on the experimental data, for the dilatancy parameters of (8), we employed the following values: $\nu_{\min} = 0.2$, $\nu_{\max} = 0.6$,

and $a' = 0.75$. The choice of a' was made by considering that $a' = a/(\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min})$ in the modified EOS, (8), while da Cruz *et al.* (2005) found $a \approx 0.3$ through molecular dynamics simulations. All other simulation parameters were kept unchanged with the only exception of μ_{side} that had to be slightly recalibrated to $\tan(14.0^\circ)$. Comparisons between the experimental velocity profiles and the ones, obtained by the multilayer model with variable ν , are reported in Fig. 3. The introduction of the dilatancy yields small but clear improvements near the free surface. Yet, it does not significantly influence the shape of the velocity profiles in the lower creep flow, especially for the case with $\zeta = 26.10^\circ$, where the dilatancy is weak. Specifically, a slight decrease in the velocities is observed near the free surface, owing to the fact that the pressure distribution with a non-uniform volume fraction field is different from the case with $\nu = 0.6$ (cf. Figs. 2 and 3). Additionally, a tendency of increase in u_x in the lower zone was observed, but this effect was partially compensated by the slightly higher μ_{side} (cf. also Sec. IV C).

B. Dam-break flows in an inclined channel

Here, we compare the simulations by the multilayer model with two experiments of dam-break flows in an inclined channel, carried out at the National Cheng Kung University (Taiwan). In this experimental setup, also reported by Rufai *et al.* (2019), a triangular-shaped deposit of glass spheres ($d_g = 2$ mm, $\phi_s = 19.6^\circ$) was let flow down in a narrow channel ($W = 20$ mm) with a steel bed surface. Two different channel inclinations of $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$ were investigated in order to study accelerating and decelerating flows. Owing to the very small width-to-grain-size ratio ($W/d_g = 10$), the sidewalls are expected to influence the dynamics almost uniformly in the transverse direction (Jop *et al.*, 2005; Maneval *et al.*, 2005); hence, the investigated flows can be regarded as quasi-2D. For each experiment, the dam-break wave was video recorded from the sidewall (region of interest with a length of ≈ 50 cm) by a high-speed digital camera (IDT Inc., X-Stream III) at 1000 frames per second, and the photographs were subsequently analyzed by the open-source PIV package, PIVlab (Thielicke and Stamhuis, 2014; Thielicke and Sonntag, 2021). To

FIG. 3. Comparisons with increasing time between the experimental velocity profiles and the modeled ones, obtained by the present multilayer model with variable ν (dilatancy parameters: $\nu_{\min} = 0.2$, $\nu_{\max} = 0.6$, $a' = 0.75$) and sidewall friction $\mu_{\text{side}} = \tan(14.0^\circ)$. (a) $\zeta = 26.10^\circ$ ($t = 0.0088$ s, $t = 0.1110$ s, and $t = 1.2211$ s), inset: volume fraction profiles; (b) $\zeta = 32.15^\circ$ ($t = 0.0169$ s, $t = 0.0551$ s, $t = 0.1779$ s, $t = 0.5720$ s, and $t = 1.2865$ s), insets: ν -profiles. The arrows indicate the direction of increasing t .

FIG. 4. Comparisons between the experimental dam-break flow with $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and the simulation by the present multilayer model. The evolutions of h , $z_{i+1/2}$, u_x , and ν are obtained with $\Delta x = 0.001$ m, 40 layers, CFL = 0.95: (a) $t = t_0$, (b) $t = t_0 + 0.025$ s, (c) $t = t_0 + 0.075$ s, (d) $t = t_0 + 0.175$ s, (e) $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s, and (f) $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s.

ensure the accuracy of the measurements, we performed a multi-pass PIV analysis with progressively refined interrogation windows (IW) of 64×64 , 32×32 , 16×16 , 8×8 pixels, and a 50% spatial overlap between contiguous IWs (Sarno *et al.*, 2018b). Although the dam-

break flows are strongly unsteady, for better accuracy the measurements at each time point, t' , were time-averaged over the small interval $[t' - 0.002$ s, $t' + 0.002$ s]. No volume fraction measurements were carried out in this experimental campaign.

FIG. 5. Comparisons between the experimental dam-break flow with $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$ and the simulation by the present multilayer model. The evolutions of h , $z_{t+1/2}$, u_x , and ν are obtained with $\Delta x = 0.001$ m, 40 layers, CFL = 0.95: (a) $t = t_0$, (b) $t = t_0 + 0.025$ s, (c) $t = t_0 + 0.075$ s, (d) $t = t_0 + 0.175$ s, (e) $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s, and (f) $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s.

The multilayer model was run on a domain $x \in [-0.25, 0.25]$ with $x = 0$ m corresponding to the gate location and over a time interval of 0.6 s so as to cover the entire time duration of the measurements. Nonreflecting boundary conditions are considered at $x = -0.25$ m

and $x = 0.25$ m. For a fair comparison between experimental and numerical data, particular attention was paid in the identification of the experimental time point, t_0 , corresponding to the start of the dam-break flow. Considering that the gate, retaining the initially static

granular pile, was lifted in ≈ 0.05 s, while in the numerical simulations, the dam-break is modeled as instantaneous, t_0 was set at the midpoint, 0.025 s after that the gate was no longer in contact with the basal surface. The comparisons with the experimental data are reported in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively, for the runs with $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$. In each figure panel, the uppermost plot shows the evolutions of h and of the interfaces, $z_{i+1/2}$, compared with the experimental contour of the avalanche (with also the photograph in the background); the middle plot shows the computed u_x field, reconstructed by linear interpolation of the numerical data from the various layers, together with the experimental u_x field obtained by PIV; the lowermost plot illustrates the computed ν field, as well reconstructed by linear interpolation. The initial conditions of the numerical simulations are

$$\bar{u}_i(x, 0) = 0, \quad \bar{\nu}_i(x, 0) = 0.6, \quad (34)$$

and the initial shapes of the deposit are reported in Figs. 4(a) and 5(a), respectively, for the two runs. The simulations were carried out with 40 layers of equal thickness and a spatial discretization of $\Delta x = 0.001$ m. Each time step, Δt , was calculated by imposing $\text{CFL} = 0.95$, and it was enforced that $\Delta t \leq 0.001$ s to ensure a good accuracy of the ODE solvers (cf. Sec. III). As in Rufai *et al.* (2019), the model rheological parameters are $\mu_s = \tan(19.6^\circ)$, $\mu_2 = \tan(28.5^\circ)$, and $I_0 = 0.279$, while $\mu_{\text{side}} = \tan(9^\circ)$ was calibrated by back-analysis. Analogous to Sec. IV A, the parameters of the dilatancy law are $\nu_{\text{min}} = 0.2$, $\nu_{\text{max}} = 0.6$, and $a' = 0.75$. The characterization of the basal boundary condition required caution. Indeed, while the basal surface allows slip, in practice different KBC were experimentally observed during the course of the same dam-break flow. At the beginning of the flow, the KBC is essentially of no-slip type, owing to the combined effects of low longitudinal velocities, u_x , high normal pressures, and consequently, high sidewall friction [cf. Eq. (27)]. The basal slip, then, becomes progressively stronger, as u_x increases and the avalanche elongates. In the later stages, as the flow depths further decrease, a less dissipating rolling friction mechanism replaces the sliding friction: namely, the grains tend to roll over the bed, especially for the steeper run with $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$. This particular KBC, where grain rolling becomes dominant over sliding, was also observed in similar experimental setups (Sarno *et al.*, 2021c). In order to adequately describe the aforementioned evolution of the basal friction, we followed the pragmatic approach of using the same $\mu(I)$ -rheology with slightly different parameters. Specifically, the following parameters were chosen for the DBC, (12), at the bed: $\mu_{s,\text{bed}} = \tan(15^\circ)$, $\mu_{2,\text{bed}} = \tan(23^\circ)$, and $I_{0,\text{bed}} = 0.7$.

From Figs. 4 and 5, it is interesting to note that the multilayer model captures well the dynamics of the dam-break flows in both cases with $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$, where very good agreement is especially observed for $t \geq t_0 + 0.175$ s [Figs. 4(d)–4(f) and 5(d)–5(f)]. Also the contours of the avalanche are generally well described for $t \geq t_0 + 0.175$ s with the exception of a slight underestimation of the tail location in the run with $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$ [Figs. 5(e) and 5(f)]. Comparatively worse agreement is observed for $t < t_0 + 0.175$ s [Figs. 4(b), 4(c), 5(b), and 5(c)]. The inferior behavior at the very initial stages of the dam-break wave might be partially attributed to the limitations of the underlying $\mu(I)$ -rheology in describing the transient motion from a state of rest, as already discussed in Sec. IV A. However, we believe that this discrepancy here is mainly due to the fact that, in the early stages, the long-wave assumption, on which the

multilayer model is based, is not strictly fulfilled owing to the high curvature of the flow lines. As a consequence, the model transforms the potential energy of the initial deposit into the x -component momentum more efficiently than it occurs in reality, as it is also confirmed by the slight overestimation of the wave front locations [cf. Figs. 4(c), 4(d), and 5(d)]. Note that, at the early stages of the dam-break, the model is almost insensitive to the rheological parameters and to the boundary resistances, since the pressure gradient terms, $\partial_x(g \cos \zeta (h_i \bar{\nu}_i)^2 / 2\bar{\nu}_i)$, and the mass forces are dominant in Eq. (16). In a further improvement of the model, we speculate that the introduction in the pressure gradient terms of a less-than-unit earth pressure coefficient, depending on the free surface curvature (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2013), might be beneficial.

For a more detailed comparison between the multilayer model and the experimental data, the velocity profiles at the specific cross sections, $x = 0$ m, $x = 0.05$ m, $x = 0.10$ m, and at $t = t_0 + 0.175$ s, $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s, $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s are displayed in Fig. 6 for $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and in Fig. 7 for $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$. To obtain more robust estimations, the velocity measurements at the generic cross section, x' , and at the time point, t' , were calculated here by spatial averaging the PIV data along the narrow stripe $[x' - 0.003$ m, $x' + 0.003$ m]. Nonetheless, it should be kept in mind that the accuracy of instantaneous PIV measurements is normally worse than that of steady state measurements, which, conversely, can be averaged on much larger time intervals (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2018b). As it is clear from Figs. 6 and 7, the multilayer model reproduces the experimental velocity profiles reasonably well for both runs with $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ and $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$. Remarkable is the model's ability to capture the variations of the shear rates, $\partial_z u_x$, with x and t . Slightly worse agreement is observed near the basal surface for $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$ at $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s and, more noticeably, at $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s, when the granular avalanche slows down [Figs. 6(b) and 6(c)]. While such a discrepancy might depend on the aforementioned limited accuracy of the instantaneous PIV data, it could also be partially due to some rheological hysteresis (e.g., Jop, 2015), possibly occurring during the depositional stages and not considered in the current rheological model.

C. Uniform flows over an erodible bed

In this section, we compare the simulations by the multilayer model with uniform chute flow experiments over an erodible bed, carried out at the University of Salerno (Italy). Different from the experiments employed in Secs. IV A and IV B, this dataset also includes the volume fraction measurements near the sidewall, which are useful to verify the dilatancy law, (8). The laboratory apparatus, analogous to that by Sarno *et al.* (2018a; 2021c), consists of a 2 m-long Plexiglas flume with width, $W = 80$ mm. At the flume outlet, a 6 cm-high weir was installed, so as to allow the formation of a granular wedge above the fixed bed, i.e., an erodible bed condition. The granular medium, made of polyoxymethylene (POM) spheroidal beads ($d_g = 3.3$ mm, $\varphi_s = 27^\circ$), was initially stored in the upper part of the channel, served as a reservoir, and, then, flowed down through an adjustable gate. After a transient period of few seconds, which was necessary for the development of the lower granular wedge and the upper surface flow, an almost uniform steady state was observed in an intermediate region of the channel far enough from the inlet gate and the outlet. For this reason, the uniform flow was investigated at a specific cross section, located at 1 m downstream of the gate. While the flume bed had a fixed inclination ($\zeta = 32.5^\circ$), as expected, the inclination of the flow

FIG. 6. Comparisons between experimental and computed velocity profiles (dam-break experiment with $\zeta = 30.8^\circ$) at $x = 0$ m, $x = 0.05$ m, $x = 0.10$ m: (a) $t = t_0 + 0.175$ s, (b) $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s, and (c) $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s.

free surface, ζ_{freesurf} , was found to increase with the mass flow rate, measured at the outlet by a load cell (Laumas AZL-50 kg). Hereafter, we consider the local frame of reference, $Oxyz$, with x being parallel to the free surface, y parallel to the transverse direction, and z the upward normal to x . Two high-speed cameras (AOS Technologies Corp.) were employed to record the flow at 1000 frames per second from both the sidewall and the free surface. The images were analyzed by PIVlab (Thielicke and Stamhuis, 2014; Thielicke and Sonntag, 2021), where a 4-pass PIV with IWs of 64×64 , 32×32 , 16×16 , and 8×8 pixels was considered (Sarno *et al.*, 2018b; 2019b). To estimate the volume fraction at the sidewall, we employed the stochastic-optical method (SOM), devised by Sarno *et al.* (2016; 2019a; 2020) and implemented

by Carleo *et al.* (2019) and Sarno *et al.* (2021c) for chute flow applications. The SOM uses a special binarization of the photographs, taken by the sidewall camera, and relies on a stochastic transfer function, determined by Monte Carlo simulations (Sarno *et al.*, 2016), to indirectly estimate the near-wall volume fraction. The method requires controlled illumination conditions with a specific incidence angle of light. For this purpose, a planar flicker-free LED lamp (PhotoSonics MultiLED-LT) was located aside the flume at a distance of 32 cm with an incidence angle of 25° with respect to the normal to the sidewall. Different flows were investigated by adjusting the gate opening. Each experiment was repeated four times, so that robust u_x and ν profiles were obtained by time-averaging the measurements over an interval of 5 s and also by averaging them over different repetitions. The experiments, used for comparison, are listed in Table I.

Since there is no net separation between the lower wedge and the upper surface flow (e.g., Komatsu *et al.*, 2001), the effective flow depths, $h_{\text{effective}}$, reported in Table I, were estimated by considering a small velocity threshold (0.001 m/s). Moreover, considering that the width-to-grain-size ratio is $W/d_g = 24$, the quasi-2D assumption appears less realistic here than in the experiments of Secs. IV A and IV B. This was also confirmed by the free surface PIV measurements (not reported for brevity) showing distinct parabolic profiles in the transverse y direction with the maximum at the flume centerline (Baker *et al.*, 2016; Sarno *et al.*, 2018a; and Carleo *et al.*, 2019). To account for these deviations from the purely 2D case, we estimated the homogenization coefficient, α ,

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{W} \int_{-W/2}^{W/2} \bar{u}_{x,\text{freesurf}}(y) dy, \quad (35)$$

where $\bar{u}_{x,\text{freesurf}}$ is the time-averaged x -component velocity, measured by PIV at the free surface, and $\bar{u}_{x,\text{freesurf}}(-W/2)$ is its value at the sidewall, $y = -W/2$. Consequently, following a similar approach by Sheng *et al.* (2011) and Carleo *et al.* (2019), the width-averaged velocity profiles, used for comparisons, were obtained by

$$\bar{u}_{x,y\text{-average}}(z) = \alpha \bar{u}_{x,\text{sidewall}}(z), \quad (36)$$

with $\bar{u}_{x,\text{sidewall}}$ being the time-averaged PIV measurements at the sidewall. It is interesting to note from Table I that α decreases with increasing flow rate, namely with increasing transverse momentum exchanges (Sarno *et al.*, 2018a). Although some deviations from the 2D case are also expected for the ν field, the sidewall profiles by SOM method, are kept unchanged, because no volume fraction measurements could be obtained at the free surface owing to the absence of a well-defined planar boundary (Sarno *et al.*, 2016; Carleo *et al.*, 2019).

Similar to that done in Sec. IV A, the numerical simulations were performed by considering an initially static deposit with thickness, h , and channel bed inclination, ζ , equal to the effective inclination, ζ_{freesurf} , of the free surface in the uniform flow experiment to reproduce. The spatial domain is $x \in [-0.5, 0.5]$ with a no-slip condition at the bed and nonreflecting boundaries at $x = -0.5$ m and $x = 0.5$ m. The initial conditions are

$$h = \sum_{i=1}^N h_i(x, 0) = 30 d_g = 0.099 \text{ m}, \quad \bar{u}_i(x, 0) = 0, \quad \bar{\nu}_i(x, 0) = 0.6. \quad (37)$$

All the simulations were carried out with $N = 60$ and were run over a time interval of 25 s, so that a sensibly uniform state was reached, and

FIG. 7. Comparisons between experimental and computed velocity profiles (dam-break experiment with $\zeta = 45.2^\circ$) at $x = 0$ m, $x = 0.05$ m, $x = 0.10$ m: (a) $t = t_0 + 0.175$ s, (b) $t = t_0 + 0.375$ s, and (c) $t = t_0 + 0.575$ s.

a direct comparison with the laboratory measurements was possible. A space discretization with $\Delta x = 0.1$ m was employed together with $\Delta t = 0.002$ s. In all simulations, we used the following rheological parameters: $\mu_s = \tan(27.0^\circ)$, $\mu_2 = \tan(32.8^\circ)$, $I_0 = 0.55$, and $\mu_{side} = \tan(10.4^\circ)$, obtained by slightly reoptimizing the parameters proposed by Carleo *et al.* (2019) for a similar experimental setup and slightly different rheological assumptions. We also chose the following parameters for the dilatancy law, (8): $\nu_{\min} = 0.2$, $\nu_{\max} = 0.6$, and $a' = 0.5$. The comparisons with the u_x and ν experimental profiles are reported in Fig. 8.

Agreement of the u_x profiles is excellent and also shows reasonably good match to the effective flow height, $h_{\text{effective}}$. Only minor

TABLE I. Uniform flow experiments over an erodible bed.

ID	Gate opening (m)	Mass flow rate (g/s)	ζ_{freesurf} ($^\circ$)	$h_{\text{effective}}$ (m)	α
Exp-06 cm	0.06	304	30.05	0.040	1.40
Exp-10 cm	0.10	815	30.90	0.052	1.15
Exp-14 cm	0.14	1361	31.35	0.062	1.08

discrepancies were observed at the lower creep flow and at the free surface for Exp-14 cm [Figs. 8(a), 8(c), and 8(e)]. The ν profiles, obtained by the multilayer model, are found to qualitatively well capture the SOM sidewall measurements, but they are unable to quantitatively reproduce the entire range of ν variations from the deposit to the free surface [Figs. 8(b), 8(d), and 8(f)]. In particular, a slight overestimation of ν is observed along the entire depth of the surface flow for Exp-06 cm. Moreover, the numerical simulations systematically overestimate the ν measurements in the more dilute region near the free surface, $h - z \leq 0.01$ m, corresponding to a thickness of $\approx 3d_g$. These discrepancies might be partially due to the fact that the SOM measurements are referred to the vicinity of the sidewall and could not be width-averaged, as done for the experimental velocity profiles [cf. Eq. (36)]. In particular, transverse variations of the ν field are expected for the case of Exp-06 cm that differs more markedly from a purely 2D flow, as also evidenced by the higher value of α (cf. Table I). On the other hand, it is reasonable to infer that the dilatancy law, (8), derived from the linear formula by da Cruz *et al.* (2005), holds for the dense regime, but it is no longer valid in the dilute flow region. In this regard, a more sophisticated dilatancy law, possibly with a stronger dependency on the shear rate as the pressure becomes small, is worth to be investigated for a further improvement of the model.

1. Sensitivity analysis on the dilatancy parameter

Here, we study in more detail the effects of the parameter, a' , of the EOS, (8), on the computed u_x and ν profiles. Specifically, we performed further numerical simulations by systematically varying a' between 0.25 and 1. With reference to the intermediate experiment, Exp-10 cm, the comparison plots are reported in Fig. 9, where also the profiles by the model with constant volume fraction, $\nu = 0.6$, are displayed.

As one can see from the figure, the velocity profile with $\nu = 0.6$ delivers slightly worse results, especially near the free surface, where u_x is noticeably overestimated, and in the creep flow region, where u_x goes to zero markedly faster than in the experiment. Using the multilayer model with the dilatancy law, (8), we found that agreement with the experimental velocity profile improves at the free surface and, to a lesser extent, also in the lower creep region. These findings are also in agreement with that observed in Sec. IV A. We believe that this improvement, over the model with constant ν , is mainly due to the different pressure distribution that is induced by the introduction of the non-uniform volume fraction along the flow thickness. While agreement with the experimental velocity profile is found to increase with increasing a' up to $a' = 0.75$ [cf. the inset of Fig. 9(a)], the best accord with the experimental ν profile corresponds to the intermediate interval of $a' \approx 0.4$ – 0.5 [Fig. 9(b)]. Nevertheless, no value of a'

FIG. 8. Comparisons between numerical and experimental profiles of steady uniform flows over an erodible bed: (a) and (b) Exp-06 cm, (c) and (d) Exp-10 cm, and (e) and (f) Exp-14 cm. The experimental u_x profiles are obtained by width-averaging the PIV measurements in Eq. (36), while the experimental ν profiles are obtained by SOM measurements at the sidewall.

manages to correctly describe the upper more dilute region. Overall, the multilayer model with the dilatancy law, (8), provides slightly better results than the model without dilatancy. Yet, it should be noted that it is still insufficient to correctly reproduce the velocity exponential decay of the creep flow, as it predicts a zero velocity from a finite depth. We believe that a better description of the lower creep region could be achievable by considering the non-local rheological effects (e. g., Bouzid *et al.*, 2015; Kamrin, 2019) and a slightly more sophisticated model for the sidewall resistances.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the multilayer model, derived by Sarno *et al.* (2021a) in the limit of the long-wave asymptotic approximation, was extensively tested in a number of laboratory experiments. The model, which implements the $\mu(I)$ -rheology (Jop *et al.*, 2005; 2006) and a dilatancy law depending on the inertial number I , was previously shown to be well-posed for all I (Sarno *et al.*, 2021a) thanks to the incorporation of the in-plane stress gradient terms, directly emerging from the $\mu(I)$ -rheology. While in Sarno *et al.* (2021a), the multilayer

FIG. 9. Comparisons between numerical and experimental profiles (Exp-10 cm) by varying the dilatancy parameter, a' : (a) u_x profiles (the inset plots describe the upper part of the creep flow region and the free surface) and (b) ν profiles.

approach was presented as a computationally efficient tool to regularize and approximate 3D models with similar rheological assumptions, the main goal of this numerical-experimental work was to assess the ability of the proposed model to practically describe a variety of granular flows. For a reliable comparison with laboratory experiments in narrow chutes, the momentum equations have been equipped with Coulomb-friction terms, accounting for the resistances exerted by the sidewalls on each layer. Moreover, to avoid an unrealistic partitioning of the flow domain, non-zero mass exchanges between the layers have been considered.

The comparisons with three different experimental datasets showed that the proposed multilayer model is a reliable and computationally cost-effective tool for practically describing granular flows. Moreover, it performs particularly well in capturing the various shapes of the velocity profiles, which can be of convex Bagnold-type, linear, or concave, depending on the complex interplay between granular dynamics and boundary conditions. The model, especially in its implementation with a variable volume fraction, was found to reasonably well reproduce the transient surface flows over a static pile (Jop *et al.*, 2007) with some discrepancies observed in the slowest experiment ($\zeta = 26.10^\circ$) and in the initial quasi-static transient state. The less satisfactory agreement in the lower creep flow region, where the model was found to slightly underestimate the experimental velocities and predicts a zero velocity from a certain depth, is chiefly caused by the $\mu(I)$ -rheology with rate-independent sidewall resistances. To improve the model performance in the slow shearing regime, we think that slightly different rheological assumptions, accounting for non-local effects and possibly also considering non-unit earth-pressure coefficients, are implementable in the same multilayer framework. The comparisons with laboratory dam-break experiments in a steep chute revealed that, while the model struggles to fully capture the early stages ($t < t_0 + 0.175s$), in the subsequent time period it reliably describes the evolution of the avalanche both in terms of velocity field and of shape of the flow domain. The aforementioned discrepancies at the initial stages of the dam break are mainly caused by the fact that the long-wave approximation and the resultant hydrostatic pressure distribution are not strictly valid in the presence of strong curvatures of the

flow lines. Therefore, we believe that a possible improvement would be the introduction of suitable corrections for the pressure gradient terms, taking into account the free surface curvature and the pressure anisotropy (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2013). The comparisons with steady uniform velocity and volume fraction profiles of chute flow experiments over an erodible bed showed that the multilayer model with the dilatancy law provides slightly superior results, compared to the same model without dilatancy. This especially holds for the description of the velocity field near the free surface and, to a lesser extent, also for the lower creep flow region. Yet, the comparisons with the near-wall volume fraction profiles, obtained by SOM (Sarno *et al.*, 2016), revealed that the proposed dilatancy law, while qualitatively capturing the general trend, overestimates ν in the upper region closest to the free surface. These discrepancies could be partially due to the fact that the SOM measurements were taken at the sidewall, while the multilayer model yields a width-averaged ν profile. On the other hand, it suggests that the proposed dilatancy law could be inadequate for dilute flows. In a future development of the research, a more sophisticated dilatancy law could be implemented without much additional effort.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Luca Sarno: Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

Yongqi Wang: Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Yih-Chin Tai:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Maria Nicolina Papa:** Investigation (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Paolo Villani:** Investigation (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Martin Oberlack:** Funding acquisition (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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